

Employee Treatment and Work Engagement: The Philippines Context

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Abstract: The study wanted to determine the correlation between employee treatment and work engagement of the employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region. To support the study, the related literature and studies were reviewed. The population of the study was all employees from two colleges located in the Ilocos region. To carry out the study, it uses the right research methodology and the study used descriptive correlational research design. The data was gathered through validated research questionnaires and in tabulating and interpreting the data, weighted mean and Pearson r were used. The study found that there is a correlation between employee treatment and work engagement of employees and therefore the hypothesis of the study was accepted.

Keywords: Employee treatment, work engagement, workers' rights, cognitive, affective, conative, respect, care.

Introduction

Organizational performance has never been separated from the individual employee's performance contribution. The individual employee's performance can be caused by many factors, not a single factor. Often time the top management makes a mistake to conclude that individual employee's performance is caused by salaries and benefits and therefore, it often focuses on how to improve salaries and benefits (Abun, et.al. 2017). Salaries and benefits can be two of the important factors to motivate employees to work smarter for the company. This assumption is supported by studies. Studies have shown that salaries and benefits improve the motivation of employees to work, improves job satisfaction, and improves employees' performance (Sudiardhita, et.al. 2018). Earlier, Hamid, et.al. (2014) had presented a similar result of their study on the impact of compensation on the job performance of employees. Their study also argued that compensation is positively correlated to employees' performance. These findings may somehow lead us to make a generalized and wrong conclusion that monetary reward is all that matters in managing the performance of employees. Other studies have proven otherwise that monetary reward is not the only factor that influences individual employee's performance. Premuzic (2013) made a review of several pieces of research related to the effect of salaries and benefits to the performance of employees. His review concluded that pay alone is

not sufficient to improve the job performance of employees though many still believe that monetary reward is the most important value in boosting employees' performance. Again this is not the case because before Premuzic (2013), Judge, et.al. (2010) had found in their study that the level of pay is only marginally related to job satisfaction. Blacksmith and Harter (2011) as cited by Premuzic (2013) had found a similar finding that no significant difference in employee engagement by pay level. The findings imply that improving employee's performance and engagement is not just about monetary reward and other related incentives but other factors have to be given attention.

Work performance and work engagement are also about workplace treatment. Collins dictionary defines treatment as "the way how someone behaves toward others or deals with them". Related to our context of the discussion, treatment refers to the way how management behaves or deals with their employees. Fair treatment and unfair treatment can affect the employee's job satisfaction/dissatisfaction and work engagement/disengagement. Rai (2013) had conducted a study related to the effect of organizational justice on job satisfaction, commitment, and turnover intention. His study found that there is a correlation between organizational justice and job satisfaction, commitment, and turnover intention of employees. The study indicates that unfair treatment is one of the factors that cause the employee to leave the organization. Hassan (2012) specifically pointed out that employees' perception of procedural and distributive justice influence job satisfaction and turnover the intention of employees.

The above findings are the result of an investigation in the profit-oriented business organization and government organization. Those studies are related to unfair treatment and job satisfaction and commitment and intention to leave. At the same time, there have been no studies done related to employees' treatment in terms of *workers' rights, respect in the workplace, and caring relationship* that affect the work engagement of employees. Therefore, the focus of the current study is to find out if employees' treatment concerning justice or workers' right, respect, and caring relationship affects the employees' work engagement of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region, Philippines.

This paper is divided into five parts. The first part is the introduction which discusses the rationale or the background of the study, and the purpose of the study. The second part is the review of related literature and studies that discuss the theories of the study particularly the concept of employee treatment, justice, respect, caring relationship, and work engagement of employees. The third part is the research methodology that includes research design, the population of the study, and locale of the study, data gathering procedures/data gathering administration, research instruments, and statistical treatment of the data. The fourth part is the presentation of empirical data and analysis. The fifth part is the result and discussion and the conclusion.

II. Review of Related Literature

Employee Treatment under the Labour Code of the Philippines in Terms of Workers' Rights

Cambridge Dictionary defines treatment as “the way you deal with or behave toward someone or something”. This is the same as the definition offered by Collins Dictionary, that treatment is defined as “the manner of handling or dealing with a person or a thing”. Related to our topic of investigation, treatment means the way how the school management or administrators behave or deal with the employees. Concerning employee treatment, the government through the Department of Labor and Employment has written laws that are called the Labour Code of the Philippines. The Labor Code of the Philippines has already established guidelines on how the management should treat the employees. The Labour Code have prescribed workers' rights, management prerogative, and dialogue mechanism between labor and management (CBA). Under the Labour Code of the Philippines, the government still recognizes management prerogative which may include hiring, firing, promotion or demotion, laying-off, laying down policies, discipline, working hours, working structure. The management has the prerogative power to hire and fire an employee who does not meet employment standards, promote or demote an employee who meets or does not meet the standards, terminate employees, discipline employees and determine working hours and work structure. But in the exercise of these management prerogatives, the management should not violate the workers' rights. By instituting management prerogative and workers' rights, the government balances the power between labor and capital or the management (Jimenez, n.d). In case of conflict between labor and management, the labor code of the Philippines provides a mechanism which is called Collective Bargaining Agreement (CBA) in which the labor through its representative and management representative can discuss their differences and come to an agreement.

Under the Labour Code of the Philippines, workers' right includes security of tenure, self-organization, collective bargaining, just and humane conditions of work, strike/concerted effort, participation in decision making, just share in the fruits of the production, living wage, labor standards and CBA rights (Jimenez, n.d). These rights are emanated from the 1987 Constitution of the Republic of the Philippines, article XIII on Human Rights and Social Justice (GOVPH, 1987). These are the rules or laws that guide the management on how they should deal with their employees and violating these rules is considered illegal. Security of Tenure recognizes that though the management has the prerogative power, every employee should be assured of security in the sense that an employee cannot be dismissed from the work any time without just cause or authorized cause and this can be done only after following the due process such as an investigation. This right is found in Article 294 of the Labor Code entitled, “Security of Tenure”. It states that the “employer shall not terminate the services of an employee except for a just cause

or when authorized” (Jimenez, 2002, Calayag, 2018). After the security of tenure, the labor also has the right to self-organization which means that the employee has the right to join, assist and form a labor organization for collective bargaining and/or for mutual aid and protection (Jimenez, n.d). The right to self-organization is found in the Republic Act, No. 875, Section 3 (Republic of the Philippines, 1953).The constitution also empowers employees with the right to bargain. Jimenez and Jimenez (n.d, 2002) contended that as a result of the right to self-organization is the right to collective bargaining in which the employees have the power to negotiate with the management for better terms and condition of employment and this right is written in the R.A. 875, Section 12-14.

Under the labor code, the employees also have the right to have humane conditions of work. In this case, the management should see to it that the working conditions of employees must be humane and just. This right includes the right to equal pay for equal work and through the Department Labour and Employment, the government of the Philippines has set the standards for minimum wage, working hours, holiday pay, overtime pay, night differential, service incentive leave, service charge, separation pay, 13th month pay, maternity benefits, paternity benefits, social security system, employee compensation commission, Philhealth, and Pag-ibig. These are aimed to protect the workers from exploitation (Jimenez, 2002, Busto, 2013). Besides the right to the humane condition of work, the employees also have the right to strike and participate in decision making. Employees who are under legitimate labor organizations have the right to strike to strengthen their bargaining power. It is also guaranteed by the 1987 constitution that employees have the right to participate in decision making related to matters that involve employees’ rights, interests, benefits, and welfare (Jimenez, n.d, Busto, 2013). Further, the Constitution which is reflected in the Labour Code of the Philippines also provides standards for the living wage. The wage should be commensurate with the living standards in a particular region.

The last two of workers’ rights are about just share of the fruits of production and full employment and equality of employment opportunities. These rights remind the management that the laborers have the right to be given shares in the fruits of productivity particularly the incremental productivity based on the extra effort of the workforce (Jimenez, 2002). The 1972 Constitution also provides a basis for the employees to claim their rights on the full employment and equality of employment opportunity which was incorporated into the Labour Code of the Philippines. Under this law, any forms of discrimination are illegal (Jimenez, n.d, Busto, 2013).

Implementing the workers’ rights that have been specified in the Labor Code is considered as the legal and moral ground of the employer’s treatment toward the employees. It is the legal and normative norms of employer behavior toward the employees. These kinds of treatment can be considered as fair treatment. This is what matters to employees. They are concerned about how they are treated in their workplace and fair treatment can affect employees' well-being, not only economically but also psychologically (Lind & Tyler, 1988, Hassan, 2012). Studies have shown that fair treatment toward employees can improve their trust toward the management, job

satisfaction, and their work engagement, and their intrinsic motivation, prevent employees from leaving the company (Choi, 2011, Kim & Rubyanti, 2011, Rubin, 2011 as cited by Hassan, 2012).

Respectin the Workplace

We are taught by our parents to respect other people whoever they are and we are also taught to respect not only human beings but even all living and non-living things such as the environment. We are taught to respect the animals because they can feel the pleasure and pains (Singer, 1974) as cited by Cochrane, (n.d). We respect and protect any sentient beings because they are capable of feeling the pains. They are protected or respected not because they are good to us but because they have inherent value in themselves (Regan, 1983). Regan (1983), as cited by Cochrane, (n.d) argued that all entities who are “subject -of-a life” possess inherent value, in the sense that they have value in themselves even though they are not good for human beings. The command to respect is originally addressed to human beings. We are taught to respect other people. Respect for other people is considered as a categorical imperative (CI) according to Emmanuel Kant. Respect is a moral law and all human beings have a moral obligation to obey the law and not following it is immoral (Allison, 2011). It is imperative. However, the command to respect and obey is not because it is a moral law but the deeper reason why we need to respect other people is our humanity. The humanity principle is “the collection of features that make us distinctively human and these include capacities to engage in self-directed in rational behavior and to pursue our ends” (Johnson, 2016). The principle of humanity would state that we should never treat other human beings as the means to an end but treat them as an end in itself. The principle of humanity does not tell us not to employ other people for our business but the principle of humanity would remind us not to engage in the pervasive use of humanity in which we treat others as a mere means to our end (Johnson, 2016). This principle is concerned with the humane treatment of human beings. Humans are not objects to be used by other people but they are subject and have dignity and therefore they have to be respected. Kant had argued that all persons are owed respect because simply they are persons, a free rational being, distinctive human beings and they are the ends in themselves with dignity (Dillon, 2018).

The Catholic Church has been placing human dignity as the foundation of all its social teaching. The Catholic Church views human beings to possess inherent dignity as a person because he/she is created in the image and likeness of God. Dignity is independent of race, gender, age, religion, color, or ability. It is simply based on its belief that human beings are created by God and therefore all human beings possess the same dignity. Therefore, no human dignity should be compromised (Caritas Australia, n.d). It is based on this teaching, that the Catholic Church calls for social actions that can restore human dignity through its activities that promote integral human development (Development and Peace, 2000). The social actions of the Catholic Church are born out of respect for human dignity. The Church has the moral responsibility to respect and restore human dignity. Respect is not because the Church wants to respect its people but it is its

moral obligation to respect and to restore its dignity as created beings. It is categorical imperative to respect without condition, not because the Church wants to do it but the Church has to do it.

Studies on human respect in the workplace and how it affects job satisfaction have been conducted. Edery (2017) explores the influence of organizational respect on Job Satisfaction in the human service. The study found that respect in the workplace is a key predictor of job satisfaction of employees. Gurchiek (2016) also surveyed respect in the workplace and its correlation to job satisfaction. Her survey indicated that respectful treatment in the workplace of all employees at all levels is considered an important contributing factor to the job satisfaction of employees. A similar study was also conducted by Ghaffari and Burgoyne (2017) on the influence of respect for employees and job satisfaction and the study confirmed that respect for employees in the workplace predicts job satisfaction of employees. The same line of study on the effect of respect and violence on the job satisfaction was conducted by Boafo (2018). His study again strengthened the previous findings of other studies that verbal abuse and perceived respect in the workplace are significant predictors of job satisfaction. A comparison study on the job satisfaction and respect among the abled and disabled persons and the study found that there was little respect given to the disabled persons and it affected their job satisfaction and therefore the study recommended a policy to implement disability awareness training for all employees to increase the amount of respect experienced by disabled workers (Brooks, 2018).

Caring Relationship in the Workplace

The philosophical and moral foundation of caring relationships in the workplace is the ethics of care which was originally developed by Noddings (1984). The ethics of care is an ethical theory which argues that moral actions should be based on the interpersonal relationship (Staudt, 2016). Actions and decisions must be based on caring. Though originally the ethics of care was an approach to education but later on her ethics of care is also developed and applied into different fields of life, at home and in the workplace, that caring is the moral foundation of a relationship. For Noddings (1984) caring relationship is a fundamental aspect of education or the moral foundation of teaching and the basis for student-teacher relations. The teacher is the carer and the student is cared-for. Her ethics of care which was used as the basis for student-teacher relationships were applied to all kinds of relationships including in the workplace. For her decision-making should be based on the ethics of care, that caring should be the basis for decision-making (Smith, 2020). Her position on the ethics of care is based on the fact of life that care is basic for human life because all human beings wanted to be cared for (Noddings, 2002, cited by Smith, 2020). In caring, there is sympathy. Burton (2015) defined sympathy as a “feeling of care and concern for someone, often someone close, accompanied by a wish to see him/her better off or happier”. In this case, the carer is deeply involved in the situation of the cared-for and join the feeling of the cared-for to get out of her troubled situation. To feel what the cared-for is feeling, the carer must be receptive or open to what the cared-for is revealing or

saying. Through listening, the carer can react in a way that is helpful for the cared for and only then, the cared-for feels that he/she is cared for by the carer (Smith, 2020).

Concerning workplace relationship, the manager is the carer and the cared for is the employees. Using the concept of Noddings (1984, 2002) the basis for action and decision making of the carer must be caring for the cared-for or the employees. The management must show compassion and concern with the well-being of employees and must feel what the employees feel and respond to the needs of the employees. Through caring, the management shows sympathy with the employees and responds in a way that can help the employee become better off. The study of Eldor and Shoshani (2016) on the caring relationship in school staff and teacher's work engagement found that compassion expressed by colleagues and the principals on the teacher is correlated positively to organizational commitment and job satisfaction. Houston (2020) as cited from Moynihan, and Pandey (2008) and Hodson, (2004) argued that positive interaction in the workplace can improve job satisfaction and prevent turnover. When the employees feel the support from the leader or the management, the employees prefer to be loyal to the company. This was also found in the study of Tran, et.al (2018) that high-quality workplace relationships improve job performance of employees and commitment and also lower job stress. Earlier, Barsade and O'Neill (2014) had conducted a study to find out if an employee who is loved performs better. Their study found that indeed an employee who is loved performed better. It is along with these findings, Rosanne (2014) argued that it is all about relationships. She pointed out that relationship-based care is a successful model for success in any organization. An indication of caring is that management is kind-hearted and showing compassion toward partners or employees and be generous in the sense that the leader or management gives time, energy, and effort to reach out to the employees or work team (Brenner, 2017). Mental Health Foundation (2016) pointed out several benefits of caring relationships in the workplace such as job satisfaction, low turnover, and improve the positive and productive workplace. Such an environment can have an impact on the mental health of employees and therefore reducing absenteeism. It is suggested that management and co-employees should be able to look out for their employees or colleagues if they are doing well not and intervene on how to help the employees or colleagues.

Work Engagement as a Multidimensional Construct

Work engagement is one of the concerns of management ever since to improve work performance or productivity. Work engagement and work performance become a single continuum that cannot be separated. The two concepts are interrelated and one can affect the other. Studies have been conducted and found that work engagement is one of the key factors in improving work performance (Kim & Kim, 2013, Bakker, 2010, Jackson, 2014.). The concern of work engagement is nothing new and the study on the work engagement is also nothing new because it was already studied in many years back but the researchers came out with a different concept of work engagement and make it difficult to measure and characterize the work

engagement (Thomas, 2009 as cited by Kuok & Taormina, 2017). The earlier researcher on the work engagement was Kahn (1990). His concept of work engagement was multidimensional. He understood work engagement as the immersion of organizational members' selves to the work physically, emotionally, and cognitively. In his concept work engagement involves the whole self. But unfortunately, this concept was not pursued by other researchers to continue measuring the work engagement from the three dimensions: physical, cognitive, and emotional. Some researchers understood work engagement as an antonym of job burnout (Maslach & Leiter, 1997) and so they proposed Maslach Burnout Inventory or MBI to find ways how to prevent job burnout. One of their recommendations is for the employees to see their work as a challenge. However, this concept was not enough to measure work engagement and therefore Schaufeli, et.al (2002) proposed a different concept of work engagement. For Schaufeli, et.al (2002), work engagement is seen as a positive state of mind related to the work which is characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption (p.74). Thus, they proposed their inventory based on their concept to measure work engagement. However, take a closer look at their proposal, they measure work engagement from the physical and emotional aspect of work engagement. Even Abun, et.al. (2017) also understood work engagement as an emotional state in which employees feel motivated, inspired, and passionate about their work and staying committed to their work. However, Bakker, et.al. (2010) feel that measuring work engagement from one dimension does not represent the concept of work engagement. He somehow pursued the earlier concept of Kahn (1990) which understood the concept of work engagement from the three dimensions such as physical, cognitive, and emotional work engagement. For Bakker, et.al (2010) work engagement is a physical, cognitive, and emotional involvement of the person to the work. The person engages the work not only physically and cognitively but also emotionally. Therefore, the concept of Kahn (1990) and Bakker, et.al (2010) are now the concepts to be followed in studying the work engagement.

Recently Kuok and Taormina (2017) have developed an inventory of work engagement to include the three dimensions which spell out the three dimensions offered by Kahn (1990). The cognitive aspect includes the ideas or the mind of the person to the work. While the emotional aspect of the engagement may include the feeling or the excitement of the person toward the work. Lastly is the physical aspect that includes the energy or stamina of the person dedicated to the work. Thus the current study is using these three dimensions to measure work engagement.

Conceptual Framework

Independent Variable

Dependent Variable

Figure1: The conceptual framework reflects the correlation between employee treatment and the work engagement of employees. The framework indicates that employee treatment influences the work engagement.

Statement of the Problems

The study tries to find out the effect of employee treatment on the work engagement of employees. It specifically wants to answer the following questions:

1. What is the employee treatment of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of
 - a. Workers' right
 - b. Respect in the workplace

- c. Caring relationship in the workplace
2. What is the work engagement of employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of
 - a. Physical engagement
 - b. Cognitive engagement
 - c. Emotional engagement
3. Is there a relationship between employee treatment and work engagement?

Assumption

The study assumes that employee treatment affects the work engagement of employees and it can be measured. It is also assumed that the theories of the study are correct and the questionnaires are valid and the answers are objective.

Hypothesis

The study of Lind & Tyler, (1988), Hassan, (2012) found that fair treatment can affect employees economically and psychologically. Then the study of Choi, (2011), Kim & Rubyanti, (2011), Rubin, (2011) as cited by Hassan, (2012) found that fair treatment can improve employees' trust toward management, job satisfaction, and work engagement. Based on their finding the study hypothesizes that there is a relationship between fair treatment and work engagement of employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The study covers only the colleges in Ilocos Region and it only limits itself to measure employee treatment along with workers' rights, respect in the workplace and caring relationship, and work engagement along physical, cognitive, and emotional dimensions. The study may not represent the situation of all Divine Word Colleges in Region I, Philippines.

III. Research Methodology

This part discusses the research methodology of how this research study was carried out. The study followed standard procedures of conducting an academic investigation which means following a research design, data gathering instruments, population, the locale of the study, data gathering procedures, and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design of the study

The study adopted the descriptive assessment and correlational research design to assess the level of organizational climate and its effect on the work engagement of employees. Shuttleworth (2020) defined descriptive research design as "a scientific method which involves observing and describing the behavior of a subject without influencing it in any way". It describes the

population, a situation, or a phenomenon. It is also used to describe the profile, frequency distribution, the characteristic of people. In short, it answers the question of what when how, and not the why question (McCombes, 2020). While the descriptive correlational study is intended to describe the relationship among variables without seeking to establish a causal connection (Ariola, 2006).

The locale of the Study

The locale of the study was Divine Word Colleges in Ilocos Region particularly Ilocos Sur and Ilocos Norte.

Population

The respondents of the study were the faculty and employees of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region. The total enumeration sampling was used and thus 250 faculty and employees were taken as respondents of the study.

Data Gathering instruments

The study used questionnaires and questionnaires on employee treatment is self-made questionnaires but it was done through content validation by a panel of experts. The questionnaires were revised by the experts. The caring relationship in the workplace was adapted from Kivimaki and Elovainio (1999). While questionnaires on respect in the workplace are adapted from Legacy Business Cultures (n.d). But questionnaires on work engagement is adapted Kuok and Taormina (2017).

Data Gathering Procedures

A good and quality research needs to gather the data through a process and therefore it needs to gather the data officially. To gather the data, the researcher sent a letter of request to different Presidents of the Colleges and asking their approval to allow the researcher to distribute the questionnaires and conducts an interview. Only after the approval, the researcher floated his questionnaires. The retrieval of questionnaires was assigned to one of the school representatives before it was handed back to the researcher.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To analyze the data, a descriptive and inferential statistic was used. The weighted mean was used to determine the level of organizational climate of the schools and the Pearson r was used to measure the correlation between organizational climate and work engagement of employees.

The following ranges of values with their descriptive interpretation will be used:

<i>Statistical Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>	<i>Overall Descriptive Rating</i>
4.21-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree	High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree	Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low/High
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree	Very Low/Very High

IV. Empirical Data and Analysis.

The structure of the data presented follows the flow of the statement of the problem. The first statement of the problem:

1. What is the employee treatment of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of
 - a. Workers’ right
 - b. Respect in the workplace
 - c. Caring relationship in the workplace

Table 1a. Employees’ Perception of Employee Treatment as to Workers’ Right

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. Security of tenure is followed	3.55	A
2. Employees feel secure when they are already employed	3.37	SWA
3. The offices are comfortable enough to work	3.46	A
4. Employees are allowed to participate in decision making through its representative	3.26	SWA
5. Management listens to the ideas of employees through their Representative	3.09	SWA
6. Salary is given according to the rank and job grade	3.33	SWA
7. Salaries are beyond the minimum wage	3.39	SWA
8. Employees’ problems are solved through due process.	3.28	SWA
9. The employees’ freedom of expression is protected.	3.22	SWA
10. The employees are allowed to organize themselves.	3.35	SWA
Composite Mean	3.33	SWA

Source: HR. Survey (n.d)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	strongly agree	Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree	High
2.61-3.40	somewhat agree	Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low/High
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree	Very Low/Very High

Based on the empirical data presented on the table, it reveals that as a whole, employees’ perception of employees’ treatment in terms of workers’ right gained the composite mean of 3.33

which means somewhat agree or moderate. This finding indicates that the management or administrators have not been performing quite high or very high in terms of protecting employees’ rights. However, taking them singly, the employees agree (high) that they have the security of tenure (3.55) and they also agree that their offices are comfortable enough to work (3.46). While other items under workers' rights, the employees seem somewhat agree. Particularly the employees somewhat agree that they feel secure after they are employed (3.37), they are listened to by the management (3.09), allowed to participate in decision making (3.26), paid according to the rank or grade (3.33) and beyond minimum wage (3.39), allowed to organize themselves (3.35), and they also somewhat agree that their freedom of expression is protected (3.22) and problems are solved through due process (3.28)

Table 1b. Employees’ Perception of Employee Treatment as to Respect in the Workplace

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. I feel valued in my institution.	3.53	A
2. All employees have equal access to professional development and training opportunities.	3.24	SWA
3. The management treats employees with respect.	3.43	A
4. The behavior of the management toward the employees is appropriate and does not make fun of employees.	3.33	SWA
5. The management typically welcomes ideas from employees who have different views, opinions, and experiences from theirs.	3.24	SWA
6. The management can work with employees coming from different backgrounds.	3.37	SWA
7. The management can openly discuss any concerns with the employees.	3.22	SWA
8. Our employees are promoted based on their skills, abilities, and experience, regardless of gender, age, ethnicity, sexual orientation, or other unique characteristics.	3.51	A
9. The management would forgive an honest mistake of employees.	3.46	A
10. Overall, our institution is a respectful place to work.	3.54	A
Composite Mean	3.39	SWA

Source: *Business Cultures (n.d).*

Legend

4.21-5.00	<i>strongly agree</i>	<i>Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree</i>	<i>High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>somewhat agree</i>	<i>Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low/High</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree</i>	<i>Very Low/Very High</i>

As it is deduced from the table, it shows that as a whole, the employees’ perception of employees’ treatment in terms of respect in the workplace got a composite mean of 3.39 which is interpreted as somewhat agree. It means that as a whole, the management or the school administrators have not been giving high or very high respect to the employees. Taking the item separately, the employees agree that they are valued by the organization (3.53), treated with respect by the management (3.43), forgiven by the management when they committed mistakes

(3.46), promoted based on merits (3.51) and they agree that their institution is a respectful place to work (3.54). However, taking other items, the employees somewhat agree that they have equal access to professional development and training opportunities (3.24) and they also somewhat agree that the management does not make fun of their employees (3.33). Beyond that, the employees are somewhat agreeing that the management respects the views of employees (3.24) and openly discusses concerns with the employees (3.22). The same perception when it comes to diversity issues that the management respect employees coming from a different background (3.37).

Table1c. Employees’ Perception of Employee Treatment as to Caring Relationship in the Workplace

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. The management offers help to employees when they are overworked or having some difficulties.	3.30	SWA
2. The management looks after the welfare of the employees.	3.36	SWA
3. The management is very considerate to employees and respecting their abilities and willingness to learn.	3.48	A
4. The management helps employees who have particular problems to overcome.	3.35	SWA
5. The management respect employees’ limitations and trying to help when they ask.	3.45	A
6. People feel understood and accepted by the management.	3.46	A
7. Employees can openly discuss and share their ideas with the management.	3.46	A
8. The employees can talk openly to the management about their difficulties because employees believe that the management will listen.	3.23	SWA
9. Employees believe that if they share ideas and task-related problems, their management will listen and would respond constructively.	3.44	A
10. The management and employees trust each other as co-workers.	3.35	SWA
Composite Mean	3.39	SWA

Source: Kivimaki and Elovainio (1999)

Legend

- | | | |
|-----------|--------------------------|---------------------------|
| 4.21-5.00 | <i>strongly agree</i> | <i>Very High</i> |
| 3.41-4.20 | <i>Agree</i> | <i>High</i> |
| 2.61-3.40 | <i>somewhat agree</i> | <i>Moderate</i> |
| 1.81-2.60 | <i>Disagree</i> | <i>Low/High</i> |
| 1.00-1.80 | <i>Strongly disagree</i> | <i>Very Low/Very High</i> |

As gleaned from the data, it appears that as a whole, employees’ perception of employees’ treatment in terms of caring relationship in the workplace achieved a composite mean of 3.39 which means somewhat agree (SWA). Consistently, as a whole, the finding points out that caring relationship is not given high or very high value by the management. However, when the items are taken separately, it reveals that the employees agree that the management respect employees’ abilities and their willingness to learn (3.48), respect employees' limitations, and help them when

needed (3.45), they are also understood and accepted by the management (3.46) and can openly discuss their ideas with the management (3.46) and the management listens to ideas (3.44). While other questions under this item, the employees somewhat agree. The employees perceive that they somewhat agree that the management offers help to them when they are overworked (3.30), looks after their welfare (3.36), helps those who have the problem (3.35), the employees can openly discuss their problems, sentiments, difficulties because they believe the management listen to them (3.23) because management and employees trust each other (3.35).

Table 1d. Summary of the Employees’ Perception of Employee Treatment

ITEMS	Mean	DR
1. Workers’ Rights	3.33	SWA
2. Respect in the Workplace	3.39	SWA
3. Caring Relationship in the Workplace	3.39	SWA
Overall Mean	3.37	SWA

Legend

- | | | |
|-----------|--------------------------|---------------------------|
| 4.21-5.00 | <i>strongly agree</i> | <i>Very High</i> |
| 3.41-4.20 | <i>Agree</i> | <i>High</i> |
| 2.61-3.40 | <i>somewhat agree</i> | <i>Moderate</i> |
| 1.81-2.60 | <i>Disagree</i> | <i>Low/High</i> |
| 1.00-1.80 | <i>Strongly disagree</i> | <i>Very Low/Very High</i> |

As a summary, the summary table manifests that overall, the perception of employees' treatment in terms of three dimensions: workers' rights, respect in the workplace, and caring relationship receive an overall mean rating of 3.37 which indicates that the employees somewhat agree in those dimensions. The employees somewhat agree that the management protects workers’ rights (3.33), respects the employees (3.39) and they somewhat agree too that there is a caring relationship between management and employees (3.39).

The overall mean rating of 3.37 indicates that management have not been performing high or very high in terms of employees’ right, respect in the workplace and caring relationship in the workplace.

2. What is the work engagement of employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of;

- d. Physical engagement**
- e. Cognitive engagement**
- f. Emotional engagement**

Table 2a. Employees Work Engagement as to Cognitive Work Engagement

Indicators	Mean	DR
1. My mind is often full of ideas about my work.	3.66	A
2. My mind is fully engaged with my work.	3.70	A

3. I have an idea about how to perform my work better.	3.80	A
4. I search for new ways to improve my knowledge related to my work.	3.76	A
5. My thoughts are fully focused when thinking about my work.	3.70	A
Composite Mean	3.72	A

Source: Kuok and Taormina (2017), Abun,et.al. (2020) .

Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>strongly agree</i>	<i>Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree</i>	<i>High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>somewhat agree</i>	<i>Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low/High</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree</i>	<i>Very Low/Very High</i>

As it is appearing on the table, the data indicates that as a whole, employees’ work engagement in terms of cognitive engagement gains a composite mean of 3.37 which shows that employees agree to all items under cognitive work engagement. Specifically, the employees agree that their mind is full of ideas about their work (3.66), fully engaged with their work (3.70), know how to perform their work better (3.80), know how to improve their knowledge related to their work (3.76) and their mind is fully focused when thinking about their work (3.70).

The evaluation indicates that as a whole the employees agree that they have the ideas about their work and how to carry out their duties and responsibilities.

Table2b. Employees Work Engagement as to Emotional Work Engagement

Indicators	Mean	DR
1. I feel very delighted about what I am doing whenever I am working.	3.66	A
2. I am excited to do my work.	3.64	A
3. I feel good about the work that I do.	3.63	A
4. I am always very enthusiastic to perform my work.	3.68	A
5. I feel very happy when I carry out my responsibilities at work.	3.69	A
Composite Mean	3.66	A

Source: Source: Kuok and Taormina (2017), Abun, et.al. (2020)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>strongly agree</i>	<i>Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree</i>	<i>High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>somewhat agree</i>	<i>Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low/High</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree</i>	<i>Very Low/Very High</i>

The evaluation reflected on the cognitive work engagement is also the same as the evaluation of emotional work engagement. The data manifest that as whole employees agree to all questions on emotional work engagement as indicated by its composite mean of 3.66 which means agree. In short, they all agree that they are emotionally engaging in their work. Separately the employees agree that they feel very delighted with what they are doing (3.66), excited to do their

work (3.64), very enthusiastic to perform their work (3.68), very happy when they carry out their responsibilities at work (3.69) and feel good about the work they do (3.63).

Table2c. Employees Work Engagement as to Physical Work Engagement

Indicators	Mean	DR
1. No matter how much I work, I still have a high level of energy.	3.43	A
2. I have a great deal of stamina for my work.	3.57	A
3. I have a lot of energy for my work.	3.54	A
4. I am frequently energized by my work.	3.62	A
5. Though my work is physically challenging, I am still excited to do it.	3.64	A
Composite Mean	3.56	A

Source: Source: Kuok and Taormina (2017), Abun, et.al. (2020)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>strongly agree</i>	<i>Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree</i>	<i>High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>somewhat agree</i>	<i>Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low/High</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree</i>	<i>Very Low/Very High</i>

As indicated in the data, it shows that as a whole, employees agree in terms of their physical engagement as pointed out by its composite mean of 3.56 which is interpreted as agreement. In other words, they as a whole agree that they are physically engaging their work. Even when the items are taken separately, it tells that employees agree that no matter how much they work, they still have a high level of energy (3.43), they still have a great deal of stamina for their work (3.57), have a lot of energy for their work (3.54), feel energized by their work (3.62) and are still excited to do their work even though the work is challenging (3.64).

Tabled2d. Summary of Work Engagement

ITEMS	Mean	DR
Cognitive Work Engagement (CWE)	3.72	A
Emotional Work Engagement (EWE)	3.66	A
Physical Work Engagement (PWE)	3.56	A
Overall Mean	3.65	A

Legend

4.21-5.00	<i>strongly agree</i>	<i>Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree</i>	<i>High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>somewhat agree</i>	<i>Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low/High</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree</i>	<i>Very Low/Very High</i>

In summary, whole employees agree that they are cognitively, emotionally, and physically engaging their work. Though the results are not very high but high, however, it indicates that as a whole, the employees are engaged in their work.

3. Is there a relationship between employee treatment and work engagement?

Table 3. Relationship between Employee Treatment and Work Engagement

ITEMS		Employee Treatment	Work Engagement
Employee Treatment	Pearson Correlation	1	.508**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	169	169
Work Engagement	Pearson Correlation	.508**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	169	169

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation table reveals that there is a significant correlation between employees' treatment and work engagement at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). It means any positive changes along employee treatment can affect work engagement.

V. Result and Discussion

The study wanted to find out the correlation between employees' treatment and work engagement of employees in Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region. The results indicate that as whole employees agree that they have been treated to a moderate extent only and have not been treated highly or very high extent by the management. This indicates that the management has not been performing excellently in terms of treatment to employees. There can be still a lot of room for improvement in terms of employees' treatment. However, despite the moderate extent of treatment, the result also demonstrated that employees agree that they have been engaging their work to a high extent. It can mean that the better the management treats its employees, the more engaged they become.

The result of the study also indicates that improving employees' treatment along with workers' rights, respect in the workplace, and caring relationship in the workplace can boost their work engagement. Failing to give attention to the employees' rights, promote respect in the workplace and caring relationship can mean work disengagement. Work disengagement can mean economic losses to the management because of low productivity. In terms of quality education, employees' disengagement can affect the quality of education. Thus, it is a great concern for the management to give attention to employees' rights, and respect employees, and establish a caring relationship in the workplace.

Conclusion.

The results of the study support the hypothesis that there is a correlation between employees' treatment and work engagement which was based on the previous studies of Lind & Tyler, (1988), Hassan, (2012), Kim & Rubyanti, (2011) that employees' treatment correlates with

economic success and work engagement. Therefore, the hypothesis of the study is accepted. This suggests that management needs to improve employees' treatment to improve employees' work engagement.

The author also recognizes the limitation of the study that the study does not represent the whole Divine Word Colleges in the Philippines and the author also recognizes that there are still of dimensions in terms of employee treatment to be measured.

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